

Supplementary Figure 1. Map of Puget Sound, Washington showing locations of submerged terraces and slope profiles.

EXPLANATION

Mapped faults

— Quaternary Fault and Fold database
2020 update (Angster et al., 2020)

Shoreline angle measurements

Onshore

- Shoreline angles mapped from lidar by Ota et al. (2006)
- Onshore deformation from ten Brink et al. (2006), Sherrod et al. (2004), and Martin (2012)

Offshore (this study)

— profiles across submerged benches,
labels indexed to text files

5 km

